

STUDY OF REPRODUCTION HEALTH EDUCATION PROGRAM FOR CHILDREN WITH MENTAL RETARDATION IN SLB-C SURAKARTA, INDONESIA

Tri Sayektiⁱ, Sunardi, Nunuk Suryani

Sebelas Maret University, Surakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:

This study aims to determine the teachers' understanding and needs on reproduction health education at high school for students with Mental Retardation in SLB CG YPPCG Surakarta, SLB PBM Surakarta, SLB YSSD Surakarta and SLB N Surakarta. This study is a kind of qualitative research with case study type. Subject in this study is teachers of students with Mental Retardation in 10th until 12th grade in 4 SLB-C in Surakarta with total of 12 respondents. Data was collected by using the instrument of knowledge and attitude understanding. Data was analyzed by sing descriptive qualitative. In this research, there are three aspects: the majority of teachers do not understand about reproduction health education yet, all respondents indicate that there are no reproduction health education programs in schools, and all respondents suggest that it is important to have education reproduction health for children with Mental Retardation.

Keywords: mental retardation, reproduction, health education

1. Introduction

Every citizen has right to obtain education. This statement is stated in UUD 1945 (Constitution of Indonesia 1945) article 31, paragraph 1. Beside, SISDIKNAS (National Education System) article 5 Regulation no. 20 year 2013 paragraph 3 states that "*citizens with physical, emotional, mental, intellectual, and/or social disorder have right to get special education*". Children with special needs based on Hallahan and Kauffman (1991) are

ⁱ Correspondence: email trisayekti@gmail.com

children, who are different from normal in general, due to some disorders in thinking, seeing, hearing, socializing, and moving (Efendi, 2008: 2).

One of those children stated in the regulation no. 12 year 2010 is mentally retarded children. According to Munzayanah (2000: 13), mentally retarded children are children with thinking development disorder and also for their entire personality, so that they cannot live independently in society even in a simple way.

Although mentally retarded children are slow in their cognitive development, mentally retarded children have same sexual development as normal children in general. However, mentally retarded children often have sexual deviance due to some factors. This topic is raised by Farisa (2013) in her research with title Factors Causing Sexual Deviance on Mentally Retarded Teenagers in SLB N Semarang. The objective of this research is to describe deviant behaviors experienced by mentally retarded teenagers. The research, conducting by using interview and observation on two mentally retarded teenagers, concluded that factors causing sexual deviance are libido and hormone change. The other factor is caused by the disorder itself, parenting, and peer relationship.

Sexual deviance behavior on mentally retarded children needs to be overcome. One solution to overcome this problem is by giving reproduction health education for mentally retarded children as observed by Schaafsma (2014) in the research with title Effective Methods for Teaching Sex Education to Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities: A Systematic Review. The research describes factors needed in giving sex education for mentally retarded children with systematic review. 20 articles were used to be concluded that it needs methods to develop education, skills, and also behavior. Those three terms need deeper attention in order methods used can work well.

In reproduction health education, teacher is the most important element to conduct this program. Teachers' role is vital in reproduction health education program, especially for mentally retarded students, to give them understanding about what reproduction health is, how to take care and protect.

The aim of this research is to determine teachers' understanding and needs about reproduction health education for mentally retarded students of senior high school in SLB CG YPPCG of Surakarta, SLB PBM of Surakarta, SLB YSSD of Surakarta, and SLB N Surakarta.

In this research, researcher observed teachers' understanding about reproduction health, existed reproduction health program, and also suggestion about the importance of reproduction health program for mentally retarded students.

2. Method

This research is a kind of qualitative research. 12 teachers who teach 10th until 12th grade mentally retarded students become subject of the research. It is conducted in SLB CG YPPCG Surakarta, SLB C PBM Surakarta, SLB YSSD Surakarta and SLB N Surakarta. Data collected by using questionnaire about reproduction health education.

The instrument is validated through content validation. Content validation is carried out using expert judgment about its content and language. Further, it would be revised and finally it can be used to collect data. Data is then analyzed by using qualitative descriptive.

3. Results

3.1 Teachers' understanding about reproduction health education

Table 1: Teachers' understanding about reproduction health education

No	Level of Understanding	Total	Percentage
1	Understand	2	16,7%
2	Fairly understand	6	50%
3	Not understand	4	33,3%
Total		12	100%

Data above shows the understanding of mentally retarded students' teachers about reproduction health. From 12 respondents, 2 respondents indicate that they understand, 6 respondents do not really understand, and 4 respondents do not understand. It can be presented in the form of graphic as follows.

Graphic 1: Teachers' understanding about reproduction health

From the result, it can be concluded that most of teachers do not really understand yet about reproduction health.

3.2 Implementation of Reproduction Health Learning Program in Class for Mentally Retarded Students of SMALB

Table 2: Implementation of Reproduction Health Learning Program in Class for Mentally Retarded Students of SMALB

No	Reproduction Health Education	Total	Percentage
1	Exist	0	0%
2	Not exist	12	100%
	Total	12	100%

Table 2 above shows the existence of reproduction health education program in class for mentally retarded students of SMALB. From 12 respondents, all respondents state that there is no reproduction health education program in school. It can be presented in the form of graphic as follows.

Graphic 2: Implementation of Reproduction Health Learning Program in Class for Mentally Retarded Students of SMALB

3.3 Teachers' Suggestion about the Importance of Reproduction Health Education for Mentally Retarded Students

Table 3: Teachers' Suggestion about the Importance of Reproduction Health Education for Mentally Retarded Students

No	Reproduction Health	Total	Percentage
1	Important	12	100%
2	Unimportant	0	0%
	Total	12	100%

Table 3 above shows teachers' suggestion about the importance of reproduction health education for mentally retarded students. From 12 respondents, 12 respondents suggest that reproduction health education for mentally retarded students is important. It can be presented in the form of graphic as follows.

Graphic 3: Teachers' Suggestion about the Importance of Reproduction Health Education for Mentally Retarded Students

5. Discussion

From the result above, it shows that most of the understanding level of teachers teaching mentally retarded students is very low. It is because there is no reproduction health education program in class for mentally retarded students in SMALB and no special training about reproduction health for mentally retarded students. Schaafsma, D (2014) in the research titled *Identifying Effective Methods for Teaching Sex Education to Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities: A Systematic Review* elaborated factors

needed in sex education for mentally retarded students. It needs methods to develop knowledge and skill. Also for the implementation of reproduction health education program in class for mentally retarded students of SMALB, it should be given special program for mentally retarded students and teachers are forced to understand reproduction health for mentally retarded students.

If teachers do not understand about the importance of reproduction health education and there is no reproduction health education program in class for mentally retarded students of SMALB, it gives impact for the students. They may have sexual deviance. This is in line with research from Farisa, D. et al. (2013) stated that factors causing sexual deviance are libido and hormone change. It is also caused by disorder itself, parenting, and peer relationship. In this case, teachers' attention in school can be one of the factors. Thus, reproduction health education for mentally retarded students is very important.

6. Conclusion

Result of this research can be drawn into three points as follows:

1. Most of teachers still do not understand about reproduction health education.
2. All respondents state that there is no reproduction health education program in school.
3. All respondents suggest that it needs reproduction health education for mentally retarded students.

References

1. Azwar, Syaifuddin.(2002). *Sikap Manusia Teori dan Pengukurannya*.Yogyakarta : Pustaka Belajar
2. Chaplin, J.P. (1981).*Kamus Lengkap Psikologi (revised)*. Jakarta : PT Raja Grafindo Persada
3. Deswita.(2006). *Psikologi Perkembangan*. Bandung : Remaja Rosdakarya
4. Effendi, M. (2008). *Pengantar Psikopedagogik Anak Berkelainan*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
5. Farisa, T.D. & Maryati, S. (2013). Faktor – Faktor Penyebab Perilaku Seksual Menyimpang Pada Remaja Tungrahita SLB N Semarang. *Developmental and Clinical Psychology*. No.2 Vol.1.hal.: 26-33
6. Hallahan dan Kauffman. (1991). *Exceptional Children*. Boston: Allyn Bacon

7. Junaedi, D. (2010). *17+ seks Menyimpang*. Jakarta : Semesta Rakyat Merdeka
8. Mappiare, A.(1982). *Psikologi Remaja*. Malang : Usaha Offset
9. Munzayanah. (2000). *Tunagrahita*. Surakarta : Depdikbud UNS
10. Santrock, J.W. (2003). *Adolescence. Perkembangan Remaja*. Jakarta : Erlangga
11. Sarwono, S. (1994). *Psikologi Remaja*. Jakarta : Erlangga
12. Sarwono. (2011). *Psikologi Remaja*. Jakarta : PT Raja Grafindo Persada
13. Schaafsma,D., et. al. (2014). Identifying Effective Methods For Teaching Sex Education to Individuals With Intellectual Disabilities: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Sex Research*. P.: 1-21
14. SISDIKNAS Pasal 5 UU no.20 Tahun 2013 ayat 2
15. Soetjningsih. (2004). *Tumbuh kembang Remaja dan Permasalahannya*. Jakarta : CV Sagung Seto
16. Sugiono. (2014). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Alfabeta : Bandung
17. Suryabrata, S. (2004). *Pengembangan Alat Ukur Psikologis*. Penerbit Andi ; Yogyakarta
18. UUD 1945 Pasal 31 Ayat 1

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Special Education Research shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).